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Regulatory evaluation of red yeast rice (*Monascus spp.*) food supplements sold via the Internet

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Summary

Red yeast rice (i.e., rice fermented with *Monascus spp.*) is currently sold via the Internet as a dietary supplement. Claims state that red yeast rice has the ability to lower blood cholesterol concentrations. The mechanism of action is well characterised because the red yeast rice constituent monacolin K is identical with lovastatin, an inhibitor of the hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA (HMG-CoA) reductase that is used in many cholesterol-lowering medicinal products. The aim of this article is to evaluate the properties of red yeast rice products that are marketed via the Internet.

Three out of five analyzed products may reach the daily dosage of 10 mg lovastatin, which is necessary for the substantiation of health claims on the maintenance of normal blood LDL-cholesterol levels as suggested by the Scientific Opinion of the European Food Safety Authority. 10 mg is also the starting dosage of medicinal lovastatin products on the German market. From a regulatory standpoint, red yeast rice products would rather have to be sold as medicinal products than as food supplements as they clearly exhibit a pharmacological action that is comparable to approved statin-containing medicinal products. This also implies potential adverse effects and interactions, about which the consumer is insufficiently informed in the case of food supplements. The lack of control over the Internet market is evidenced by the fact that four of the tested products were not marketable in conventional trade in Germany due to violations of labelling rules.

Zusammenfassung

Rotschimmelreis (*Monascus spp.* fermentierter Reis) wird im Internet als Nahrungsergänzungsmittel vertrieben, wobei die Möglichkeit der Senkung des Blutcholesterinspiegels werbend herausgestellt wird. Der Wirkmechanismus ist sehr gut charakterisiert, da der Rotschimmelreisbestandteil Monacolin K identisch mit Lovastatin ist, das als Inhibitor der Hydroxymethylglutaryl-CoA (HMG-CoA) Reduktase in cholesterinsenkenden Arzneimitteln eingesetzt wird. In diesem Artikel werden die

Eigenschaften von Rotschimmelreisprodukten aus dem Internethandel bewertet.

Drei von fünf analysierten Produkten können eine Tagesdosis von 10 mg Lovastatin erreichen, die nach einer wissenschaftlichen Bewertung der Europäischen Behörde für Lebensmittelsicherheit (EFSA) zur Anspruchs begründung für eine gesundheitsbezogene Angabe notwendig ist. 10 mg ist auch die geringste Dosierung von Fertigarzneimitteln auf dem deutschen Markt. Nach den gesetzlichen Vorschriften entsprechen Rotschimmelreisprodukte daher eher Arzneimitteln als Nahrungsergänzungsmitteln, da sie eine pharmakologische Wirkung aufweisen, die der von zugelassenen statinhaltigen Arzneimitteln entspricht. Dabei sind auch mögliche Neben- und Wechselwirkungen zu berücksichtigen, über die der Verbraucher im Falle von Nahrungsergänzungsmitteln nur unzureichend informiert wird. Die mangelnde Kontrolle des Internethandels wird in dieser Produktkategorie auch besonders deutlich, da vier der untersuchten Produkte allein aufgrund des Verstoßes gegen Kennzeichnungsvorgaben im regulären Handel nicht verkehrsfähig gewesen wären.

Introduction

The fermentation products of *Monascus*, particularly those produced through the solid-state fermentation of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), have been used as food and traditional Chinese medicine for over 1000 years [1]. The products are referred to as “Hong Qu”, “Hon-Chi”, “Anka” or “Ang-kak” in China and Taiwan, and as “Beni Koji” or “red Koji” in Japan. In Europe, the products are called

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“red rice”, “red mould rice”, “red Chinese rice” or “red yeast rice” (the most common name that we also will use throughout this work) [2]. It should be noted, however, that the designation “yeast” is taxonomically incorrect [1]. Apart from being used as additive for the colouring, flavouring and preservation of foods, which may be permitted in some Asian countries but not in Europe, red yeast rice products are predominantly marketed as food supplements, primarily via the Internet, with a claim that red yeast rice has the ability to lower cholesterol levels [3]. The claim is based on the presence of monacolins that are formed by *Monascus* during the fermentation process [2]. Monacolin compounds have the ability to cause a reversible competitive inhibition of the microsomal hydroxymethyl-glutaryl coenzyme A (HMG-CoA) reductase, thus preventing the reduction of HMG-CoA to mevalonic acid and the formation of cholesterol [3]. The major *Monascus* metabolite is monacolin K, which is structurally identical to lovastatin, the first statin drug introduced into the market [4,5]. The red yeast rice products that are marketed as food supplements today differ from the traditional red yeast rice that is sold in Chinese groceries as they may be manufactured using selected *Monascus* strains under carefully controlled conditions to increase the statin content, which is monitored during production [6].

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has recently provided a scientific opinion on the substantiation of health claims related to monacolin K from red yeast rice [7]. The opinion was primarily based on two double-blind, placebo-controlled human intervention studies, which demonstrated a significant reduction in total cholesterol concentrations in the red yeast rice treatment groups compared to the placebo groups [8,9]. Besides the clinical trials reviewed by EFSA, further studies have proven the efficacy of red yeast rice [10–12], see also the review of the Chinese literature in *Liu et al.* [13]. Mechanistic evidence regarding cholesterol synthesis in human hepatic cells *in vitro* additionally showed that the inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase is not only facilitated by pure lovastatin but by red yeast rice preparations as well [14]. The EFSA concluded that a cause and effect relationship has been established between the consumption of monacolin K from red yeast rice and the maintenance of normal blood LDL-cholesterol levels, providing a daily dose of about 10 mg [7]. It must be noted that the EFSA opinion [7] has not considered the categorisation of such products as food or medicine. Therefore, it cannot be interpreted as approval of the food use of red yeast rice. In relation to the restrictions of use, the EFSA [7] also remarked that reference is made to the summary of product characteristics of lovastatin-containing medicinal products available in the EU market. The final approval or decline of the health claims related to red yeast rice by the European Commission has currently not taken place.

This study reports the toxicological and regulatory aspects of samples analyzed using our previously developed NMR methodology [2].

Materials and methods

The sampling was similar to Ref. [2]. An Internet research was conducted in November 2011 to identify all red yeast rice products that were offered at German speaking websites to German speaking consumers (for exact methodology, see Löbell-Behrends et al. [15]). None of the products was available in conventional retail sale. Using mail order over the Internet, we were able to purchase a total of five different products were marketed to German consumers as food supplements in capsule form (i.e., the red yeast rice is provided in powder form in a capsule). One product was labelled in German (with complete mandatory food information), three products were labelled exclusively in English, and one product in French with some German statements (but not the complete mandatory food information in German). A bread for toasting containing red yeast rice was additionally offered on one website, but we were not able to obtain a sample as it was out of stock.

The samples were analyzed for total statin content by NMR. Sample preparation and analytical method were previously described in detail [2].

Results and discussion

The detailed analytical results including method validation data were previously reported [2]. All five analyzed samples contained statins and the sum of statins ranged from 1.5 mg/capsule (Sample 1, food supplement from Austria) to 8.0 mg/capsule (Sample 5, food supplement from France) (Tab. 1). Our data showed good agreement with the manufacturers' labelling for two of the products (Sample 1 and Sample 5; for the other three products no labelling was provided). The observed concentrations correspond to a range between 1.5 and 25.2 mg per specified daily dose. Three of five investigated products (Sample 3, 4 and 5) contained more than the 10 mg per daily dose considered necessary for substantiation of health claims by the European Food Safety Authority (see introduction). This is also the starting dosage of medicinal lovastatin products with a clear dose-response in humans [16–18]. Our results confirm previous studies that have found a wide variability in total monacolin content [19,20] as well as a lack in product standardization [21].

The adverse effects from red yeast rice use are expected to be similar to the adverse effects of pure lovastatin contained in medicinal products [2]. From the clinical trials conducted on medicinal products that contain lovastatin, the adverse effects are well characterised. The major adverse effect of lovastatin is the increased risk of myopathy, which – in its most severe form – may produce potentially fatal acute rhabdomyolysis [22]. *Becker et al.* [10] treated “statin-intolerant” patients safely with a daily dose of 3600 mg red yeast rice (equivalent to 6 mg monacolin K and 13 mg total monacolins). The same group demonstrated the comparable safety and efficacy of a daily dose

Tab. 1 Results of the quantitative NMR determination of total statins in red yeast rice products (reproduced with permission from [2]).

Sample	Sample labelling	Product origin	Total statins (NMR)		Labelling of monacolin K [mg/capsule]
			[mg/capsule]	[mg/daily dose] ^a	
S1	Red rice, food supplement, 330 mg capsules (in German)	Austria	1.5	1.5–4.5	1.33
S2	Red yeast rice, food supplement, 600 mg capsules (in English)	USA with UK labelling	3.3	6.6	no labelling
S3	Red yeast rice, herbal supplement, 330 mg capsules (in English)	UK	5.3	10.6	no labelling
S4	Red yeast rice, dietary supplement, 600 mg capsules (in English)	USA	6.3	12.6–25.2	no labelling
S5	Red yeast rice, food supplement, 600 mg capsules (in French)	France	8.0	16.0–24.0	9.6

^a The daily dosage was calculated combining our analytical result with the intake recommendation according to the labelling of the product (a range is given when the manufacturer recommended a range for daily dose)

of 40 mg pravastatin and 4800 mg red yeast rice (equivalent to 10 mg monacolin K) in this group of patients [10]. Therefore, this “statin-intolerance” seems to be an effect of inadequate dosing.

However, drug interactions may cause a higher risk of rhabdomyolysis, especially when drugs are co-administered. This can influence liver enzyme expression leading to a lower clearance and elevated plasma concentration of lovastatin (e. g. by inhibition of cytochrome P450 enzyme CYP3A4) [22,23]. When lovastatin is administered with food, the intestinal absorption may be increased by about 50 %, while pectin and oat bran may decrease its absorption [23–25]. The excessive use of grapefruit juice may also inhibit CYP3A4 and lead to higher plasma concentrations of lovastatin [26,27]. Interestingly, the use of red yeast rice products was also found to cause myopathy [28–32]. Other adverse side effects of red yeast rice use include symptomatic hepatitis [33] and anaphylactic reactions [34]. Commercial red yeast rice preparations may contain mycotoxins, such as citrinin, that have concentrations of up to 114 µg/capsule [19,21]. A review of the Chinese literature has concluded that the formation of citrinin from *Monascus* is strain-dependent and highly variable [1]. In our samples, the typical NMR resonances of citrinin were not detected (detection limit was about 25 µg/capsule). The sensitivity of NMR is not high enough to detect trace amounts of citrinin (< 10 µg/capsule), which may occur in some red yeast rice samples [19,21].

Other compounds with unknown toxicological profiles include monacophenyl [35], steroids [36], monascodilone [37], monascopyridines [38–41], monascuspyrrole [42], monasnicotinate [43], azaphilones [44,45], ankaflavin [46], some pigments [47–50], about 80 volatile compounds [51], or coumarin derivatives [52].

Our study is in full agreement with *Liu et al.* [13], who pointed out the low quality and potential publication bias of the majority of randomised controlled trials with red yeast rice conducted in China, leading to the conclusion that more rigorous trials are needed and that long-term effects as well as safety should be investigated. At this stage,

we conclude that the benefits of red yeast rice do not outweigh its risks. The consumer that uses the current products marketed as food supplement is not adequately informed about the risks, particularly the risk of myopathy when co-administering other medications [28]. The consumer is also not informed that those with a history of statin intolerance may face extreme danger caused by the use of red yeast rice [29]. The problem is increased by the lack of standardised manufacturing practices [21] and the lack of governmental oversight over the Internet market [19,53], which make it difficult for clinical trial results to be generalized in the commercially available preparations [21]. The general lack of control over the Internet market [15,54] is evidenced by the fact that even under the current EU regulations governing food supplements, four out of the five red yeast rice products would still be not marketable in conventional trade in Germany due to violations of various food labelling rules. For instance, some products have missing essential labelling elements, such as product designation in German language, the date of minimum durability or the ‘use by’ date as well as the inclusion of mandatory information on the protection of consumers’ health and safe use of a particular food, such as not to exceed the stated recommended daily dose.

As a final remark it must be noted that the red yeast rice products placed under investigation were about 4–25-times more expensive (per 10 mg daily dosage) in Germany compared to medicinal prescription lovastatin products. This is consistent with evidence from the US that show generic statins are 5–15-times cheaper than the red yeast rice supplements [55]. In Germany, the costs of medicinal lovastatin may also be covered by health insurance if the use is indicated and prescribed by a physician. Nevertheless, the red yeast rice products may have a niche for patients that prefer alternative medications above taking prescription statins. Until the safety issues are resolved, the German consumer should be informed that the use of red yeast rice products currently poses a higher risk without any obvious benefit (economical or otherwise).

Conclusion

The literature agrees the fact that the efficacy, but not the safety of red yeast rice has been adequately proven [1,3,6,9,13,19,20,29,55,56]. As red yeast rice products are clearly pharmacologically active, we believe that they would have to be marketed as medicinal product in line with European directive 2001/83/EC rather than as food supplement, thus requires a more strict regulatory control and standardisation. The pharmacological action was proven down to 10 mg/day (for lovastatin) and the dose-response relationship makes it plausible that pharmacological action exists also at lower concentrations, at least down to 1 mg/day (applying an inter-individual safety factor of 10). For this reason, we believe that all five analysed samples are medicinal products based on the European directive 2001/83/EC. Our judgement that red yeast rice is typically a medicinal product is in accordance with the Senate Commission on Food Safety of the German Research Foundation [3], which found red yeast rice unsuitable for use as a foodstuff/food supplement. Inside the framework of traditional Chinese medicine, which is by its proponents regarded as more natural, safer and less expensive than European-style synthetic medicines, red yeast rice is clearly an exception since it fulfils neither of these expectations.

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